

Comparative Analysis of Phenotypic Techniques Used to Find Biofilm Formation in Urinary Isolates

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Abstract:

Among patients with and without catheters, urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most prevalent infections in humans. In the bladder, Uro-pathogenic organisms can form intracellular bacterial communities known as biofilm. These communities are primarily made of polysaccharides and block the entry of white blood cells, antibodies, and antibiotics. Because the biofilms reduce the susceptibility to antimicrobial drugs, they are of great medicinal value. Additionally, close-knit cell groups inside a biofilm can promote plasmid exchange, which in turn accelerates the spread of antibiotic resistance. To establish, standardise, and validate several in vitro phenotypic detection techniques and procedures for urine isolates' biofilm formation screening and confirmation.

We evaluated 161 urinary isolates by four methods (that can be used in routine clinical laboratories) for their ability to form biofilms. Out of the 161 isolates, the TCP method detected biofilm in 45 isolates (27.95%), TM detected biofilm in 45 isolates (27.95%), CRA detected biofilm in 39 isolates (24.22%), and MCRA detected biofilm in 32 isolates (19.87%). The TCP was found to be most sensitive followed by the TM, CRA and the MCRA method. TCP method is the ideal method for detection of bacterial biofilm formation by uropathogens. MCRA method is superior to CRA and not to TCP or TM for detection of the staphylococcal biofilm formation.

Keywords: TM, UTI, MCRA, TCP, CRA, Uro-pathogens.

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Introduction

A biofilm is a bacterial population that is organised and adheres to a living or inert surface using a self-produced polymeric matrix [1-3]. Staphylococcal infections are currently regarded as one of the main nosocomial infections due to the growing usage of implant devices in medical practice [4]. Antibiotics and the human immune system are two common pressures that biofilm-associated illnesses are resistant to, which can result in persistent infections [5, 6]. Classifying UTIs into first and recurring infections is another common approach. Once more, recurrent infections are separated into reinfection, bacterial persistence, and unresolved bacteriuria. Common symptoms of urinary tract infections include pain, fever, and discomfort, all of which are easily treated. When the infection spreads to the kidneys, treatment becomes more difficult.

A biofilm is a collection of microorganisms in which the cells are bonded to the substrate or to one another permanently. Their growth rate and gene transcription have changed, and they are encased in a matrix of extracellular polymeric sub-

stances (EPS) that they have generated.[7] The presence of surface bacteria, chemotaxis towards the surface, motility of the bacteria, surface adhesins, and the availability of essential nutrients are some of the elements that affect the formation of biofilms [8,9]. The germs that are encased in the biofilm are very difficult to treat. This could be as a result of the drug concentration being too low in some parts of the movie[10]. Because they lack a metabolic process, the bacteria at the base of the biofilm are resistant to some antibiotics and have active mechanisms for breaking down medicines, which helps prevent the buildup of an effective drug concentration.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection: A total of 1485 clinical isolates from urine samples will be subjected to different biofilm detection methods. The study will be conducted at the Department of Microbiology, L.N. Medical College, Bhopal from June 2019 to March 2020.

Tissue culture plate method: Fresh agar plate iso-

lates were inoculated with 2% sucrose in brain heart infusion (BHI) broth, and the mixture was then incubated for 18 to 24 hours at 37°C under stationary conditions. The broth that was clearly turbid was diluted with a new medium to a ratio of 1 in 100. 0.2 ml of the diluted cultures were added to each well of a flat-bottom polystyrene plate. The broth was used as a control to ensure that the medium was sterile and non-specifically bound. These plates were incubated at 37°C for a whole day. Following incubation, the well's contents were carefully removed, and 0.2 ml of phosphate buffer saline (PBS pH 7.2) was used four times to wash off any free-floating "planktonic" bacteria. For thirty minutes, adhering "sessile" organisms in a plate generated biofilms that were fixed with sodium acetate (2%) and stained with crystal violet (0.1% w/v). After thoroughly cleaning the excess stain with deionised water, the plates were set aside to dry. Adherent bacterial cells were consistently stained with crystal violet and typically formed a biofilm on all of the side wells. Using a micro-Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay auto reader, the optical densities (OD) of the stained adhering bacteria were measured at 570 nm (OD 570 nm) and graded. These optical density (OD) readings were regarded as a measure of the bacteria's ability to stick to surfaces and create biofilms. Three separate people experimented.[11]

Tube method: A loop full of microorganisms from overnight culture plates was added to 10 ml of BHI broth with 2% sucrose, and the mixture was then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C[12]. After being decanted, the tubes were cleaned with PBS (pH 7.3) and allowed to dry. After that, dried tubes were dyed for 30 minutes with crystal violet (0.1%). After removing any leftover dye, the tubes were dried and checked for the development of biofilm. When a discernible film covered the tube's wall and bottom, biofilm development was

deemed to be occurring.

Congo Red Agar technique: This calls for the use of a solid medium BHI broth that has been properly prepared and enhanced with 5% sucrose and Congo red. The microbe from an overnight culture plate was used to inoculate the CRA plate, which was then incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 37°C. A positive result was indicated by black colonies with a dry crystalline quality. Three separate people experimented.[13]

Modified Congo Red Agar method: The MCRA modifies the CRA by altering the concentrations of sucrose and Congo red dye, leaving out glucose, and substituting Blood Base Agar for BHI Agar.

After inoculating the MCRA plate with organisms from a fresh plate that had grown overnight, it was incubated for 48 hours at 37°C and then for two to four days at room temperature. Black colonies with a dry crystalline consistency showed a positive outcome. Three separate people experimented.[14]

Result

Biofilm was detected using the TCP method, CRA method, and tube method. shows the biofilm detection by different phenotypic methods and the sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of Congo red agar and tube methods compared to the tissue culture plate method. The difference between the biofilm detection rates by the CRA method and the Tube method was statistically not significant

The spectrum of organisms isolated: From the study total 1485 samples were collected such Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 35984 isolates by 320 (21.54%), Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 35556 isolates by 370 (24.91%) Escherichia coli ATCC 35218 isolates by 445 (29.96%) and Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 12228 isolates by 350 (23.56%).

Table 1: Spectrum of organisms isolated

Organism	Isolates	Percent
Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 35984	320	21.54%
Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 35556,	370	24.91%
Escherichia coli ATCC 35218	445	29.96%
Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 12228 (non-slime)	350	23.56%

Organism-wise distribution of biofilm production: From the total isolates, biofilm producers were distributed as 45,23,45,48 to Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 35984, Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 35556, Escherichia coli ATCC 35218 and Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 12228 (non-slime producer) respectively.

Table 2: Organism-wise distribution of biofilm production

Organism	Total	Biofilm	Percent
Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 35984	320	45	14.06%
Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 35556,	370	23	6.21%
Escherichia coli ATCC 35218	445	45	10.11%
Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 12228 (non-slime producer)	350	48	13.71%

Detection of biofilm production by different phenotypic methods: For the detection of biofilm production here Tube method (45) and the Tissue culture plate method (45), Congo red agar (39), Modified Congo Red Agar method(32).

Table 3: Detection of biofilm production by different phenotypic methods

	Biofilm producers	Percent
Congo Red Agar	39	24.22%
Tube Method	45	27.95%
Tissue Culture Plate Method	45	27.95%
Modified Congo Red Agar Method	32	19.87%

Out of the 161 isolates TCP method detected biofilm production in (27.95%) of cases. The rate of biofilm detection by TM (27.95%) was not significantly different from that by TCP. However, in CRA method detected biofilm production in (24.22%) of cases and in MCRA the rate of detection was (19.87%) each which is significantly lower than that in TCP. Except for staphylococcus aureus, we could not find any difference in the rate of

biofilm detection between CRA and MCRA. However, TCP method detected stronger (18.63%), moderate (31.05%) and Weak(50.31%) biofilm producers when compared to other methods. TM was 34.8% sensitive, and 100% specific, with positive and negative predictive value, and accuracy of 100%, 52.5% and 71.3% respectively as compared to CRA and MCRA methods.

Table 4: Grading of biofilm formation in various isolates by the four different methods

Number of isolates	Biofilm formation	TCP n(%)	TM n(%)	CRA n(%)	Modified CRA n(%)
n=161	High	30(18.63)	26(16.14)	18(11.18)	16(9.93)
	Moderate	50(31.05)	30(18.63)	38(23.60)	24(14.90)
	Weak/none	81(50.31)	105(65.21)	105(65.21)	121(75.15)

Figure 1:

Table 5: Statistical evaluation of TM, CRA, and modified CRA methods for the detection of biofilm formation

Screening methods	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
Tissue Culture Plate	49.7%	100%	100%	58.8%	60.9%
Tube Method	34.8%	100%	100%	52.5%	71.3%
Congo Red Agar	31.6%	100%	100%	48.9%	60.9%
Modified Congo Red Agar Method	24.8%	100%	100%	48.9%	97.0%

Conclusion

In conclusion, biofilms are a key cause of recur-

rent and resistant UTIs, which increases patient morbidity, lengthens hospital stays, and increases the financial load on sources. Because of the

partial elimination of the infection requirements, biofilms play a crucial role in simple UTIs. Now more than ever, a workable solution that is affordable, simple to implement, and requires little technological know-how is required. The most sensitive approach was determined to be TCP, which was followed by TM, CRA, and MCRA. The best technique for identifying bacterial biofilm formation by Uro-pathogens is the TCP approach. For detection, the MCRA approach is better than CRA but not TCP or TM.

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